

INDIAN COOPERATIVE REVIEW

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Impact of NPAs on the Performance Variables in Chennai Central Cooperative Bank

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Abstract

The Problem of Non - performing Assets (NPAS) is less in Chennai Central Co- operative Bank as compared to the other CCBs in Tamil Nadu. The Present Paper makes an attempt to study the impact of NPAs on the Net profit, Investment, Legal Expenses and Spread of the bank by applying simple regressing model. The data on NPAS and other relevant performance variables from 1999 to 2005 is used for the analysis. The impact of study concludes that the effective management of NPAS is essential to strengthen the financial position of the bank.

Introduction

In line with the international practices and as per the recommendation

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made by the Committee on financial system under the Chairmanship Shri.M.Narasimham, The RBI has introduced, in a phased Manner, Prudential norms for income recognition, asset Classification and Provisioning for the advances portfolio of the Central Co-operative Banks So as to move toward greater consistency and transparency in the published account.

The Concept of Non - Performing Assets in its present form came in to existence with the recommendations of Narasimha Committee implemented by RBI in 1996-1997. Level of NPAs as per these guidelines were first reflected in the CCBs balance sheets of 31.3.1997

Meaning of NPA

A credit facility is treated as 'past due' when it remains outstanding for 30 days beyond the due date. A non-performing asset (NPA) is defined generally as a credit facility in respect of which interest or installment of principal is in arrears for two quarters or more.

CCCB-A Profile

The Chennai Central Co-Operative bank limited was registered in the year 1930 and it has completed 75 years of service in the city of Chennai. At present, the bank has 63 branches operating in Chennai city. Totally 519 Co-operative societies are affiliated to the bank including 280 employees Co-operative societies functioning in the city of Chennai, By the end of the year 2004-05 the total deposits of the bank stood at Rs.1071.20 Crores, of which loans and advances were Rs.956.94 Crores. During the year, the total investments of the bank amounted to Rs.579.51 Crores. The total net profit by the bank were Rs.50.21 Crores and the gross NPAs stood at Rs.11.5 Crores. The gross NPAs to gross advances ratio also was considerably less from 4.07 percent in 1999 to 1.26 percent in 2005. NPAs affect the liquidity, profitability and equity of the societies hence, the present study elucidates the Magnitude of NPAs and their relationship with selected performance variables of the bank namely net profit, investment, legal expenses and spread.

Objective of the Study

The present study is conducted to examine the impact of NPAs on the selected performance variables viz., Net Profits, Investments, Legal Expenses and Spread of Chennai Central Co-operative Bank.

Methodology

The study focuses only on Chennai Central Co-operative Bank [CCCB]. The Data from 1999 to 2005 are used to study the impact of NPAs

on the selected performance variables of the bank by applying simple regression model.

The fitted simple regression model is

$$Y = a + b X + e$$

Whereas,

y = Dependent variable (Net Profits, Investments, Legal Expenses and Spread)

x = Independent Variable (Gross NPAs)

b = Regression Co-efficient

a = Intercept

e = Error term

The resulted regression co-efficient are presented below.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Impact of Net Profit

There is very strong adverse relationship between Net Profit and gross NPAs. While NPAs bring down Net Profit substantially and affect bank reserves and provisions the Regression Analysis may not fully reflect the position. The resulted regression co-efficient values are presented in Table-1

Table-I

Impact of NPAs on Net Profit

Sl.No.	Regression Co-efficient	Net Profit
1.	Regression Estimate	-1.3085
2.	Standard Error	1.8283
3.	T-Statistics	-0.716
4.	Constant	6323.24
5.	R ²	0.0929
6.	F-Statistics	0.512

The results reveal that NPAs, and the Net Profit have negative relationship. Magnitude of relationship is very low and statistically insignificant. Thus 9.29 percent of the variation of Net Profit is explained by NPAs. The regression co-efficient of gross NPA reveals that a unit increase in Gross NPAs results in decrease in Net Profit by 1.31 unit. The higher constant values indicate the High Profit of the bank even when effect of NPAs is low. It indicate the impact of several other causes on the Net Profit of the bank.

Impact of Investments

As the level of Non-performing assets goes on increasing, the banks are inclined to take a safe route of reducing advances and increasing investments. The results are furnished in Table-2.

Table -2

Impact of NPAs on Investments

SI.No.	Regression Co-efficient	Investments
1.	Regression Estimate	- 12.2321
2.	Standard Error	14.2173
3.	T-Statistics	- 0.860
4.	Constant	71247.68*
5.	R ²	0.1290
6.	F-Statistics	0.740

* Significant at 5 percent level

The results show that NPAs have negative relationship with investments. The R² value of 12.90 percent of variability in investments could be attributed to NPAs. The only significant variable is constant. It indicates the influence of other variables except NPAs on the investments of the bank.

Impact of Legal Expenses

There is direct and very close relationship between legal expenses and NPAs. More Non-performing assets mean more legal expenditure. The time taken to decide court cases is long and the expenses also mount. The result of simple regression analysis is shown in Table-3.

Table-3
Impact of NPAs on Legal Expenses

Sl.No.	Regression Co-efficient	Legal Expenses
1.	Regression Estimate	- 3.9377
2.	Standard Error	8.9298
3.	T-Statistics	-0.044
4.	Constant	1.6894
5.	R ²	0.0004
6.	F-Statistics	0.002

It is understood that NPAs have negative relationship with legal expenses. This indicates that 04 percent of variation in legal expenses is on account of NPAs effect. The impact of NPAs is very low and it is also statistically insignificant. This reveals that the increase in NPAs is the main cause of decrease in legal expenses.

Impact of Spread

Spread means the difference between interest earned and interest expended. There is a relationship between NPAs and Spread as the income is received from performing Assets and the NPAs do not contribute to the spread at all. This is indicative of the position that performing assets partially make up for the loss of income on account of NPAs. The equation is shown in Table-4.

Table-4
Impact of NPAs on Spread

Sl.No.	Regression Co-efficient	Spread
1.	Regression Estimate	- 2.2172
2.	Standard Error	2.0786
3.	T-Statistics	-1.067
4.	Constant	9714.30*
5.	R ²	0.1854
6.	F-Statistics	1.14

* Significant at 5 percent level

The results reveal that NPAs have negative relationship with spread. The R² value is 0.1854 which shows that 18.54 percent variation in spread is explained by NPAs. The regression Co-efficient is insignificant which shows that spread has insignificant impact on NPAs. The only significant variable is constant.

Conclusion:

This paper has examined the impact of NPAs on selected performance variables viz., Net Profit, Investments, Legal Expenses and Spread of bank. Simple regression model was applied to analyse its impact on performance variables. The result showed that impact of NPAs on all the above performance variables of the bank was negative and insignificant at 5 percent level in all the equation. The only significant variable is constant in investment and spread. So concerted efforts are required at RBI, NABARD and banks level to control the Mounting of NPAs to make the CCCBs effective in the management of NPAs and performance.

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APPENDIX - 1		BASE DATA							
		(Rs. in lakhs)							
Sl. No.	Particular	1998-99	1999-2000	2001-01	2001-02	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	
1.	Gross NPAs	1648	1867	1849	1929	1795	1583	1151	
2.	Net Profit	2705	2831	3286	4690	5555	4705	5021	
3.	Investments	33323	51334	51416	44589	57307	56556	59601	
4.	Legal Expenses	0.75	1.06	1.63	2.25	2.01	1.80	1.86	
5.	Spread	4294	4292	5058	6644	6857	7409	7232	

Source : The Financial Audit Report of the CCCB Ltd.